

The Ethics of Abolishing Estate, Gift and Inheritance Taxes

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Abstract

Estate, inheritance and gift taxes are minor forms of raising revenue. They are related, since they all deal with the taking of accumulated wealth. Estate taxes are levied on the estate of a deceased person. Inheritance taxes are levied by most states on those who receive the property of a deceased person. And gift taxes are levied either on the donor or donee for property that is transferred before death. All three are based on the ability to pay principle, which is morally bankrupt. It would be difficult to argue that these taxes are justified on a benefit received basis, since dead people derive no benefit from government. The author discusses some ethical issues involved in these forms of taxation and suggests that the ethical solution is to abolish them.

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² The federal estate and gift tax collections for fiscal 1998 represented less than 2% of federal revenue. Office of Management and Budget, *1998 Fiscal Year Budget*, as cited in JAMES W. PRATT AND WILLIAM N. KULSRUD, *INDIVIDUAL TAXATION*, 1998 Edition (Houston: Dame Publications, Inc., 1997), at 1-10.

deceased person.³ Inheritance taxes are levied by most states on those who receive the property of a deceased person. And gift taxes are levied either on the donor or donee for property that is transferred before death. All three are based on the ability to pay principle, which is morally bankrupt.⁴ It would be difficult to argue that these taxes are justified on a cost-benefit basis, since dead people derive no benefit from government.

Karl Marx advocated a 100% inheritance tax as a means of destroying capitalism.⁵ And with good reason. These taxes are an effective way to confiscate wealth.⁶ If the goal is to reduce inequality of wealth or make capital vanish, these taxes will help to achieve that goal.⁷ These forms of taxation do not raise much revenue and government coffers would not be much less full if these taxes were abolished completely, because there are many ways to avoid paying these taxes.⁸ So why have them?

There seem to be no clear benefits to implementing any of these taxes, but there are some drawbacks. Wealth tends to leave the country that has such taxes. People who have managed to accumulate wealth do not want to have it confiscated, so they tend

³ The top rate at one point was over 90%. The top rate in 1997 was 39.6%. PRATT & KULSRUD, *supra*, at page before the back cover.

⁴ For a discussion of the ability to pay principle, see Robert W. McGee, *Some Tax Advice for Latvia and Other Similarly Situated Emerging Economies*, 13 INTERNATIONAL TAX & BUSINESS LAWYER 223-308 (1996), at 233-234.

⁵ KARL MARX, THE COMMUNIST MANIFESTO (1848).

⁶ "Historically, the primary function of wealth transfer taxes has been to *hinder* the accumulation of wealth by family units. Thus, the goal of wealth redistribution generally underlies the design of estate and gift tax systems." PRATT & KULSRUD, *supra*, at 1-10.

⁷ I am not saying that equalizing income is a legitimate goal of government, because it is not. For a detailed discussion of this point, see BERTRAND DE JOUVENEL, THE ETHICS OF REDISTRIBUTION (1952; 1989).

⁸ Some commentators even go so far as to say that these taxes are "voluntary," since they are paid only by those who are too stupid to plan for their death. G. COOPER, A VOLUNTARY TAX? NEW PERSPECTIVES ON SOPHISTICATED ESTATE TAX AVOIDANCE (1979), as cited by JOSEPH E. STIGLITZ, ECONOMICS OF THE PUBLIC SECTOR, second edition (1988), at 559.

to put it in places where it will not be confiscated. Or they will not make an effort to save and accumulate wealth in the first place, since there is no reason for doing so if it will only be confiscated anyway.⁹ A number of studies have shown that the right to inherit plays an important role in motivating savings. One study suggests that as much as two-thirds of all capital accumulation is due to inheritances.¹⁰

So savings, investment and wealth accumulation suffer because it removes the incentive to accumulate wealth. Economic growth must suffer as a result. Emerging economies are least able to afford this dissipation of resources. In fact, they might consider becoming tax havens, places where people can feel safe sending their accumulated wealth to protect it from confiscation in other countries. Such a policy would provide much needed capital at little cost. In the USA, the state of Florida has been able to attract the accumulated wealth of retirement-age people because it does not have an inheritance tax. When people retire, they move to Florida and bring their lifetime savings with them, causing a mini-boom in the trust and wealth management industries. Emerging economies could learn a lesson from such a policy.

Another problem with estate and gift tax law, at least those in the USA, is that they are extremely complicated. Even tax planners cannot always be certain that they are shielding their clients from tax liability, and thousands of court cases involving estate and gift taxes have been heard over the years. The resources that are spent administering these tax laws could be better spent elsewhere.¹¹

⁹ JOSEPH E. STIGLITZ, at 558.

¹⁰ Laurence Kotlikoff and Lawrence Summers, *The Role of Intergenerational Transfers in Aggregate Capital Accumulation*, 89 JOURNAL OF POLITICAL ECONOMY 706-32 (1981).

¹¹ For a good example that illustrates the complexity of just one estate tax provision, see *Clayton Estate v. Commissioner* (5th Cir. 1992).

As strong as all these arguments against estate, inheritance and gift taxes may be, they are all utilitarian-based. In effect, these arguments all take the position that these taxes are bad because they are inefficient. The moral dimension is totally absent. Thus, the utilitarian arguments that have been put forth over the years that call for the abolition of these taxes are incomplete. Several moral arguments can be made for their immediate abolition.

For one thing, estate, inheritance and gift taxes are all forms of double taxation. The income that was earned and retained in order to accumulate this wealth was already taxed. Taxing these assets again when the owner dies or gifts the property to someone else is a second tax.

But the real moral argument involves the underlying purpose of government. Any form of taxation is on shaky moral ground to begin with because it involves the taking of property without the owner's consent. So any tax, to be even theoretically justified, must in some way benefit those who pay. But those who pay estate, inheritance and gift taxes do not benefit as a result of the tax.

There are only two basic forms of government. The first exists where the government is master and the people are servants, to be exploited as the government wishes. As Karl Marx said: "From each according to his ability, to each according to his needs." The second exists where the people are the masters and the government is the servant. In effect, the government's role is to provide services to the people. The first form is inherently immoral because it depends on exploitation. The second form can be moral, at least in cases where the people don't mind being taxed to pay for government services.

Estate, gift and inheritance taxes are all based on the Marxist principle of ability to pay. Thus, they are immoral on their face. In the case of the estate tax, those who pay cannot possibly benefit because they are dead. They cannot receive any government services, yet they have to pay for them. Many people give large gifts in order to avoid the estate tax. The gift tax is a way the government has found to squeeze money out of those who

avoid the estate tax. The inheritance tax is just like the estate tax except that it is the recipient rather than the owner of the estate who pays.

All three of these taxes are exploitative, and thus are morally bankrupt. The only solution is to abolish them, the sooner the better.